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Assessing AI Literacy and Readiness in the Thailand's Workforce: Challenges and Opportunities for Digital Transformation

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Abstract

As the rapid advancement of Artificial Intelligence (AI) has recently been proved as a critical component of our digital transformation which impacts multiple dimensions of human's life like economic, social, and cultural aspects etc. Since AI technologies keep evolving, it provides opportunities for human to enhance productivity efficiency, and innovation across multiple sectors while it also denotes the challenges that required to discuss to employ their benefits and mitigate potential risks in the future. The comprehends of these opportunities and challenges is crucial to leveraging AI. It is imperative to understand both in how AI could be further implemented to Thailand's workforce to improve capabilities and readiness. Hence, this research aims to assess the present state of AI literacy and readiness in Thailand's workforce and fine recommendations in proposals for policymakers to enhance AI skills development initiatives by focusing on the workforce's awareness to integrate AI into their operational job. This study could highlight the importance of equipping individuals' necessary skills until to thrive to be AI-driven economy country. The research employs a modified Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) framework in evaluation of factors influencing AI adoption, proficiency and the workforce's intention to use AI systems. In order to gather relevant data, the researcher has conducted online questionnaire surveys, targeting Thailand's workforce across industries, with the target of 318 respondents from various demographical workforce. This questionnaire aims to focus on important variables such as the perceived usefulness of AI, perceived ease of use AI, social influence, facilitating conditions, AI literacy and behavioral intention to use AI. In addition, this research also aims to examine the potential fears that could hinder AI skills development. It is essential to identify these barriers for developing strategies to encourage AI adoption and could be benefit for policymakers to create environment to embrace AI technology advancement. The findings from this research aims to directly support both the private and public sector to adopt AI skills effectively and bridging

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the gap between digital literacy skills and the necessary skills to enhance the workforce's readiness for the future of AI-driven economic development, not only enhancing technical skills should be involved but fostering mindset open to continuous learning and adaptation as part of policies. Fostering an open mindset is proved to be necessitating to a more AI- integrated workforce. Not only is it beneficial to this cause of integrating AI into the workforce but also for overall workforce readiness to the new workforce landscape where many technologies and skillsets are being integrated into workplace. Therefore, a comprehensive strategy that includes updating educational curricula, promoting intersectoral collaborations, and investing in lifelong learning platforms will proves to be beneficial to the long-term advancement of the workforce in general. This research aims to find solutions that ensures all segments of the population are equipped with the tools needed for upcoming changes and disruption, thus preventing a divide between different socio-economic groups. Ultimately, this research aims to support Thailand's transition towards AI-driven economy by ensuring that its workforce is well-prepared for upcoming development and changes. By equipping workforce with the AI-related necessary skills and knowledge, Thailand can harness the full potential of AI technologies to drive innovation and economic growth while mitigating potential risks associated with technological disruption. With strategic planning and implementation of effective policies, Thailand can position itself as a leader by shift into the next level and embracing digital transformation in region.

JEL classification: O33, J24, L86

Keywords: AI literacy, workforce readiness, digital transformation, technology adoption

1. Introduction

As Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly transforming the workforce worldwide, reenforcing digitalization and reshaping how businesses operate. As many opportunities AI's rapid changes may bring, so do challenges, in particular for developing countries like Thailand where AI has extreme potential to enhance and maintain global competitiveness. In integration of AI technologies into Thailand's industries, the potential to enhance productivity, streamline operations and foster innovation is high. However, to what extent that potential can be achieved will highly depend on the readiness and literacy of the workforce. Without these necessary digital literacy skills, the potential benefits of AI-driven workforce could be hindered and further aggravate the divide between workforce and digitalization (Schiavo, Businaro, & Zancanaro, 2024).

Presently, the Thai workforce is at a critical intersection, in need of both policy-driven and comprehensive education and training programs to promote AI literacy and readiness, Thailand's economic growth will have to rely on the proper alignment of its workforce's skills in correspondence with the increasing demand for AI proficiency in the modern world. There have been researches that indicates the AI literacy influences acceptance and proficiency in using AI systems, making it vital to understand how prepared the Thai workforce is in adoption of AI technologies. (Schiavo, Businaro, & Zancanaro, 2024).

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As a key component in its broader vision for digital transformation, Thailand has outlined a national AI strategy and action plan for 2022-2027. The plan involves five key strategies which is designed to establish a robust AI ecosystem that further enhances both the economy and the quality of life of Thai citizens. Among those five key strategies are 15 work plans, expanding the focus from ethics, infrastructure human capacity, innovation, and AI applications. Some of the specific targets included raising AI awareness among its 600,000 citizens, enforcing AI-related legislatures and regulations, and cultivating over 30,000 AI talents within the span of six years. The plan further prioritized AI adoption in 10 key industries including from government services, agriculture, healthcare, finance, and manufacturing to drive innovation and efficiency. As a result of this plan's announcement, Thailand has improved its global standing in AI readiness from 59th to 31st in the Government AI Readiness Index between 2021 and 2022. Many key initiatives like the development of a national AI service platform, the establishment of supercomputer infrastructure, and the Super AI Engineer workforce development programmers which are pivotal to achieving these goals. A strong emphasis is then placed on ethical AI development, with efforts to create comprehensive AI ethics guidelines and governance frameworks to guide responsible AI use (Ministry of Higher Education, Science, Research and Innovation, & Ministry of Digital Economy and Society, 2023; National Science and Technology Development Agency, 2022).

Therefore, this study employs a modified Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) framework. The UTAUT framework provides an extensive structure that can be used to analyze factors such as performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), social influence (SI), and facilitating conditions (FC) which could influence AI adoption. Furthermore, AI-related anxiety will also be introduced as one a key variable, recognizing that anxiety caused by gaps of AI literacy can be arbitrated.

This research's methodology consists of an online survey questionnaire that was distributed across various workforce in Thailand's industries. Using statistical techniques such as descriptive statistics, multiple regression analysis and Structural Equation Modelling (SEM), the researcher was able to investigate the relationship between independent variable (PU, PE, SI, FC) and dependent variables such as AI acceptance, performance expectancy and intention to use which reflects as workforce readiness. This approach provides a comprehensive understanding of many factors influencing AI adoption and digital skill development in Thailand, offering key insights and compass the direction for policymakers, furthermore businesses sector can foster a digitally empowered workforce.

2. Literature Review

2.1 AI Literacy /AI Skill

AI literacy or AI skill typically refers to an individuals' ability to comprehend, utilize, and critically evaluating AI technologies, a skill that is increasingly demanded in modern digital economies (Jang, 2024). The importance of AI literacy spans over many sectors as it tends to prepare individuals with essential skills to leverage and enhance productivity as well as efficiency through the use AI tools (Jang, 2024). In present day's workforce, the capability to

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interact and utilize with AI systems effectively does not only benefits individual's performance and capabilities but businesses' ability to maintain its competency through optimized operations, driven by AI tools.

While AI tools are accepted across various industries, there has been a growing concern that workers across the workforce must acquire certain AI-related competencies and skills. Some workforce demographics, late-career-stage workers, for example, can be proved beneficial from AI literacy training. Through those training, these workers can bring about a mix of extensive industry experience in combination with AI skills, can create valuable contributions to the digital economy (Chetty, 2023). There can even be new career path, emerge from the rise of AI. For instance, prompt engineering, is a role where individuals with extensive domain knowledge refines AI outputs based on their extensive experience (Chetty, 2023). This trend suggests that AI literacy is not only about technical proficiency but also the capability in applying AI within the specific given context to generate favorable outputs.

In an effort to bridge the skills gap in today's workforce, developing educational strategies that can promote AI literacy should be highlighted as one of the most prominent as it provides tangible benefits of AI tools, as studies have shown that performance expectancy significantly influences the intention to adopt these technologies (Jang, 2024). This has been proven correct, specifically for younger learners and students, who not only required to understand how AI tools function but also to utilize it for their practical applications and limitations in their own academic and professional contexts in the future.

Therefore, an integrative and multidisciplinary approach to AI is proved to be crucial. As Margaryan (2023) elaborates that the need for an approach that brings together insights from social sciences, engineering and computer science to create comprehensive AI literacy programs is essential for a more digitalized economy. These programs should not only cover technical skills but also on critical thinking skills, which altogether creates a so-called "fusion skill" which combines ethical AI use with comprehensive understanding of AI. This will allow the workforce to collaborate with AI effectively and proficiently (Margaryan, 2023). This approach further advocates for a more holistic reform of the business education to further integrate AI literacy into their programs in ensuring that future business and workforce personnels are well-equipped to work alongside AI systems. (Margaryan, 2023).

This transformation in work environment practices due to the advancement of AI required a continuous adaptation of skills and knowledge. Chetty (2023) and Babashahi et al. (2024) argues that AI literacy can and should be a part of lifelong learning, providing that many professionals today will have to experience rapid technological advancement for years to come. Moreover, metacognitive skills, the set of skills that allows an individual with the ability to reflect on one's cognitive process while using AI systems, are proved critical. While AI continues to advance and evolves, the workforce, too, shall adapt to understand the capabilities and the limitations of AI in order to utilize them effectively in decision making and problem solve processes. (Babashahi ei al., 2024). AI literacy, therefore, proved vital for workers at every stage in their careers. It is not a set of skills that is preferable but required to enhances

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individual performance and ensure that the economy can continue to leverage AI technologies for innovation and long-term growth.

2.2 Anxiety with AI technology

The unanticipated adoption of AI across multiple industries has introduced to the workforce both optimistic and pessimistic impressions. AI anxiety, defined as the fear or an uneasy feeling associated with the use of AI technologies, can significantly influence job performance and the individual's ability to comprehend and adopt AI into their daily professional lives. The root causes of the anxiety stems from concerns of one's job security, the potential of AI to be misused, or the ability of adapt to the rapid changes of technological environments (Alkhalifah et al., 2024). These anxieties tend to be prevalent particularly among the older workers or those with lower technical self-efficacy, creating barriers to AI adoption in the workplace (Dingel et al., 2024).

AI anxiety can have a direct, negative impact on work performance. Research have shown that anxiety related to AI tools, in particular for high-stakes environment like in healthcare or government, can hinder the effective use of AI-enabled systems. For example, in clinical settings, there can be anxiety associated with AI-based decision-making systems which, in turn, reduced the job performance. The cause for AI anxiety in this example can be traced to how many healthcare practitioners hesitates to rely on AI tools for critical decisions (Dingel et al., 2024). Furthermore, many studies have also highlighted that the job autonomy and psychological well-being of the employees can positively influence the effects of AI anxiety by providing employees by mitigating the fears of job replacement and provide them with greater sense of control. (Lee & Jo, 2023). By ensuring that employees would have full autonomy over their work process, the overall AI anxiety in workplace can be significantly reduced (Lee & Jo, 2023).

AI anxiety can have negative correlations with AI acceptance. A meta-analysis of healthcare practitioners' use of AI-enabled clinical decision support systems of AI-CDSSs founded that anxiety is one of the significant predictors of lower acceptance and intentions to use AI systems (Dingel et al., 2024). Many practitioners who have high levels of experiences with AI are less likely to trust and adopt these systems in the future, even when provided with proper literacy trainings and potential benefits AI could bring. This suggests that in addressing AI anxiety, training and educational interventions could further enhance the overall acceptance of AI technologies in the workplace but might not be able to address every AI anxiety given the uniqueness of each situation and circumstances.

Some research suggests that AI anxiety plays a mediating role between the relationship of AI literacy and AI acceptance. While those with high AI literacy are more likely to trust and accept the AI systems into their professional career, some with lower AI literacy are more repellent of AI systems with AI anxiety being the core barrier to further AI learning and usage, diminishing its positive effect of literacy on AI acceptance (Dingel et al., 2024). This further underscore the importance of not only improving the AI literacy but also to actively addressing the sources of anxiety in an effort to foster a more AI-proficient workforce.

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One of the particularly striking forms of AI anxiety is existential anxiety, which defines the fears of AI's impact on the future of humanity as a whole. One of the studies conducted in Saudi Arabia shows that over 96% of respondents expressed existential fears related to AI, including concerns about death, the unpredictability of fate, and ethical dilemmas of AI usage. (Alkhalifah et al., 2024). Such anxieties are particularly pronounced among older age groups and individuals in precarious employment situations, especially employees that are divorced or widowed (Alkhalifah et al., 2024).

Another concept that is closely related to AI anxiety is the concept of technostress, which defines the stress individuals' experiences while adopting newer technologies. Technostress can be categorized into two categories: challenge and hindrance stressors. Challenge stressors are perceived as opportunities for growth while hindrance stressors evoke negative connotations such as anxiety. Research has indicated that while some workers may view AI as a challenge that further promotes skill development, others experience heightened anxiety due to technical difficulties and fear of obsolescence which further hinder AI adoption (Chang et al., 2023). Therefore, technical self-efficacy plays a moderating role in this relationship where workers with higher self-efficacy are less likely to experience AI anxiety and are likely to adopt AI as a growth opportunity (Chang et al., 2023).

2.3 AI Acceptance / AI Adoption

The acceptance of AI is a crucial factor in its successful implementation within various industries. The Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) provides a fundamental framework for the understanding of AI acceptance. The framework highlights key factors such as performance expectancy (PE), effort expectancy (EE), social influence (SI), and facilitating conditions (FC) as primary predictors of the behavioral intentions to use AI technologies (Venkatesh et al., 2003). UTAUT has been widely applied to study AI adoption across sectors, revealing that these factors significantly influence employees' and organizations' willingness to embrace AI (de Andrés-Sánchez & Gené-Albesa, 2023). Performance expectancy or the perceived usefulness of AI, then often emerges as the strongest predictor of acceptance, particularly in industries that heavily relies on AI for operational efficiency.

AI literacy is also another crucial factor in AI acceptance. The higher levels of AI literacy, the higher the intention to adopt AI tools. As noted by Li and Kim (2024), AI literacy does not only enhance workers' competency but also reduces AI anxiety and consequently leads to higher acceptance rates. In the European exhibition industry, for instance, a lack of AI literacy has been noted as one of the significant barriers to AI adoption, especially in smaller organizations wherein financial and technological resources are limited (Hradecky et al., 2022).

Trust also plays a pivotal role of AI acceptance. Researchers found that trust significantly influences behavioral intentions to utilize AI, especially in industries where AI is used to handle sensitive tasks (de Andrés-Sánchez & Gené-Albesa, 2023). This trust factor is particularly relevant to many AI-driven systems like chatbots and AI-enabled decision support systems, where each user must solely rely on the technology to deliver both accurate and reliable

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outcomes. Trust, therefore, is not only build on the performance of AI but also on its transparency and alignment with user expectations (de Andrés-Sánchez & Gené-Albesa, 2023).

The readiness in adoption of AI highly varies across different industries as it is influenced by several organizational factors. Hradecky et al. (2022) found that organizational size, financial resources, and the strength of internal technological practices, such as IT infrastructure, in the European exhibition sector are key technological resources which are more likely to adopt AI since they can mitigate the associated risks and costs. Moreover, data management and protection concerns, especially after COVID-19 pandemic, have further heightened the need for safer, more secure AI systems that can comply with data privacy regulations. This strategic approach, combined with tangible management support and employee training programs, are proved essential in fostering a positive environment for AI adoption (Hradecky et al., 2022).

The future success of AI adoption also highly depends on whether organizations are technologically ready and there is sufficient training provided to its employees. All employees need to be equipped with the sufficient skill set to use AI effectively and proper training programs can address the insecurities and anxieties involved the use of AI and its adoption (Hradecky et al., 2022). As Li and Kim (2024) emphasized, developing AI literacy within organizations is essential for human resource development (HRD) and that it should be prioritized. Competencies with AI and technology should include the understanding of its relevance, values, and ethical implications in order to navigate through the evolving technological landscape.

3. Study

While Thailand undergoes a significant digital transformation, AI literacy and workforce readiness are deemed critical for the successful adoption of AI technologies. This research aims to investigate all the scopes involved from AI literacy, anxiety, and acceptance in the Thai workforce with the following research questions:

- What is the current level of AI proficiency & readiness and how workforce perceive about AI technology across industries?
- What are the key challenges and opportunities to enhance AI skills and readiness in Thailand?
- How can policymakers adopt the AI skill development initiative to be further effective in Thailand's economic landscape?

3.1 Research Hypothesis

H1.1 PE influences AI Acceptance

In accordance to the UTAUT framework, Performance Expectancy (PE) which refers to the belief that using AI will help improve job performance, is one of the strongest predictors of AI acceptance. It is, therefore, logical to postulate that is individuals perceive AI technologies to

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be useful in enhancing their job performance, they are more likely to accept and adopt these technologies. (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Schiavo et al., 2024)

H1.2 EE influences AI Acceptance

Effort Expectancy (EE) is the degree of ease related with the use of new system or technology. In this hypothesis, the researcher suggests that the individuals who perceive AI tools are easy to use, they are more likely to accept and adopt these technologies. (de Andrés-Sánchez & Gené-Albesa, 2023; Li & Kim, 2024)

H1.3 SI influences AI Acceptance

Social Influence (SI) refers to the extent to which individuals perceive that important others (such as managers, peers, or society) believe they should use AI technologies. As greater the social influences from, for example, colleagues or societal expectations, will lead to greater acceptance of AI tools. (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Hradecky et al., 2022)

H1.4 FC influences AI Acceptance

Facilitating Conditions (FC) refers to the belief that the necessary organizational and technical infrastructure is in place to support the use of AI technologies. This asserts that when workers believe they have the resources, training, and support sufficient enough to use AI, they are more likely to accept it as a part of their workflow. (Hradecky et al., 2022; Venkatesh et al., 2003)

H1.5 EE influences PE

This hypothesis speculates that Effort Expectancy (EE) directly influences Performance Expectancy (PE). When individuals perceive the ease of new system or technology, they are more likely to accept believe that it will improve their job performance. (Venkatesh et al., 2003; Schiavo et al., 2024)

H1.6 PE influences Intention to Use AI

Performance Expectancy (PE) can significantly influence an individual's intention to use AI technologies. If workers view AI as beneficial and relevant aid to their tasks, they are more inclined to use it. (Li & Kim, 2024; de Andrés-Sánchez & Gené-Albesa, 2023)

H1.7 AI Acceptance influences Intention to Use AI

Overall, AI acceptance can directly influence an individual's intention to use AI technologies. Higher levels of acceptance, driven by positive experiences and perceptions, are likely to lead to a greater intention to use AI in the future. (Venkatesh et al., 2003; National Science and Technology Development Agency, 2022)

H2 PS influences AI Acceptance

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This hypothesis postulate that Privacy and Security (PS), which refers to the users' trust in their data's security and privacy. Privacy and security can significantly impact AI acceptance by which if an individual feels confident that their data is protected and secure, they will be more likely to adopt and accept AI technologies. Many studies shows that trust in security factor can be a critical factor in user adoption, particularly in settings where security perceptions are strongly in relation to adoption rates such as mobile payment system (Allahham & Ahmad, 2024; de Andrés-Sánchez & Gené-Albesa, 2023; Schiavo et al., 2024).

H3 AI Literacy influences AI Acceptance

AI literacy can have positive impact upon AI acceptance. This means that higher AI literacy makes individuals comfortable and knowledgeable in utilization of AI technologies. Which in turn fosters a more positive overall attitude and hospitality towards AI utilization by augmenting users' comprehension and perceived usefulness of AI. The research have also highlighted that generational differences and individual knowledge, and skills can further impact trust and acceptance, where those with better proficiency in information technology tend to trust and adopt AI (Chaudhry et al., 2022; Mamela et al., 2020).

H4 AI Literacy influences AI Anxiety

An increased AI literacy can help reducing AI-related anxiety. Increase in familiarity with AI concepts and skillset can attenuate AI related anxiety through the process of enhancing user confidence and lower the feeling of uncertainty surrounding AI which can later be contributed to anxiety. In many cases, such as pediatric nurses, the correlation between AI literacy and anxiety is notably to be reductive. This means that AI literacy could reduce AI-anxiety and increase competency in the workforce (Dingel et al., 2024; Falebita, 2024; Özçevik Subaşı et al., 2024; Schiavo et al., 2024).

H5 AI Anxiety influences AI Acceptance

AI anxiety can have negative impacts on AI acceptance. When many individuals feel anxious or fearful towards the concept of AI, they are, therefore, less likely to accept nor utilize it. For example, in many supply chain firms, Ai-induced anxieties has been discovered to be impeding adoptions of mobile payment services. It can be suggested, thereafter, that training programs can reduce such anxieties and foster a more optimistic perception of AI. Since heightened anxiety can lead to hesitation or even resistance to adopt and integrate AI technologies altogether it can be hypothesized that AI anxiety plays a pessimistic role in AI acceptance (Allahham & Ahmad, 2024; Budhathoki et al., 2024; Schiavo et al., 2024).

H6 AI Literacy influences Performance Expectancy (PE) & Effort Expectancy (EE)

Ai literacy can have positive impact upon acknowledgement in AI technology. Once individuals are well-equipped with AI knowledge and skill, they are potentially to acknowledge and being aware of advantages in their personal and professional matter. Thus, it can be hypothesized that

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AI Literacy positively relates with Performance Expectancy (PE) & Effort Expectancy (EE) accordingly (Schiavo et al., 2024).

H7 AI Anxiety impact the relation between AI Literacy and AI Acceptance (Mediator)

AI anxiety can act as a mediator as well in the relationships between AI literacy and AI acceptance. In this trend, it is suggested that as AI literacy increases, reducing AI anxiety levels can prove critical in improving acceptance of AI technologies. Lower anxiety levels mean individuals will be more hospitable and receptive to AI tools, further expanding the positive effects of AI literacy on AI acceptance. (Chang et al., 2024; Dingel et al., 2024; Schiavo et al., 2024; Suseno Yuliani et al., 2023).

3.2 Methodology and Sample

This research is employing a quantitative methodology by using an online survey questionnaire to assess on AI literacy, anxiety, and acceptance among the Thai workforces. The design on this survey is based on the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) framework which evaluates key factors such as performance expectancy, effort expectancy, social influence, and facilitating conditions, altogether while measuring AI anxiety and trust as mediating variables. The sample size was of 318 respondents across the industries of Thai workforce and is targeted to ensure proper representation. The data collected will be analyzed using the Structural Equation Modelling (SEM) in order to identify the relationships between AI literacy, anxiety, and acceptance in how these factors are influenced by different demographics and organizational characteristics. This approach, then, provides a comprehensive understanding of Thai workforce's readiness in adopting AI technologies as well as supporting recommendations in enhancing AI literacy and reducing AI-related anxiety across the workforce.

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Figure 1
Conceptual Model

3.3 Measures

The research was designed to promptly test the proposed hypotheses through specifically made questionnaires wherein it was designed to gather data on AI literacy, anxiety, and acceptance within the context of Thai workforce. The questionnaires target specific variables of interests from:

- **Demographic Information:** Collecting background information on respondents, including occupation, industry, age, gender, education level, and frequency of internet use. These demographic factors were considered essential for understanding variations in AI literacy, anxiety, and acceptance across different workforce segments.
- **AI Acceptance:** To measure AI acceptance, the following items were adapted from the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT). Key constructs included:
 - **Performance Expectancy (PE):** The belief that using AI will enhance job performance.
 - **Effort Expectancy (EE):** The degree to which respondents felt AI tools would ease to use in their tasks.
 - **Social Influence (SI):** This assessed how much respondents felt encouraged by colleagues or societal norms to use AI.
 - **Facilitating Conditions (FC):** The availability of organizational support and resources to facilitate AI use.
- **AI Literacy:** AI literacy was assessed using the AI Literacy Scale (AILS) developed by Wienrich et al. (2023), which gauges individuals' self-reported understanding and ability to use AI technologies effectively.

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- AI Anxiety: AI-related anxiety was measured using the AI Anxiety Scale (AIAS) developed by Wang (2019).
- Privacy and Security (PS) was measured users' trust in their data's security and privacy using the questionnaire items developed by Túrkeş et al. (2020).
- Intention to Use AI: This section evaluated respondents' intention to adopt and use AI technologies in the future. This measure was later transformed into a numerical scale for analysis, allowing for a structured comparison of usage intentions across respondent groups.

Table 1
Demographic of Sample

<i>Characteristic</i>	<i>Attribute</i>	<i>Frequency</i>	<i>Percentage (%)</i>
<i>Gender</i>	<i>Female</i>	142	55.35
	<i>Male</i>	176	44.65
<i>Age</i>	<i>Below 15</i>	13	4.09
	<i>25-34</i>	123	38.68
	<i>35-44</i>	98	30.82
	<i>45-54</i>	66	20.75
	<i>55</i>	18	5.66
<i>Nationality</i>	<i>Thai</i>	318	100
<i>Education</i>	<i>Bachelor's degree</i>	158	49.69
	<i>Master's degree</i>	139	43.71
	<i>Doctoral degree</i>	21	6.6
<i>Occupation</i>	<i>Staff/Employee</i>	145	45.60
	<i>Supervisor/Team Leader</i>	141	44.34
	<i>Manager/Department Head</i>	31	9.75
	<i>Executive</i>	1	0.31
<i>Experience</i>	<i>0-3</i>	7	2.20
	<i>3-5</i>	25	7.86
	<i>5-10</i>	124	38.99
	<i>10-15</i>	118	37.11
	<i>15+ years</i>	44	13.84
<i>Industry</i>	<i>Information Technology</i>	47	14.78
	<i>Consumer Products</i>	39	12.26
	<i>Services</i>	26	8.18
	<i>Industrial</i>	34	10.69
	<i>Medical and Health</i>	43	13.52
	<i>Finance</i>	13	4.09
	<i>Consulting</i>	2	0.63
	<i>Energy and Utilities</i>	63	19.81
	<i>Agricultural and Food Industry</i>	41	12.89
	<i>Other</i>	10	3.14

4. Analysis

Through the data collected by online survey questionnaires with the target of 318 respondents from various Thailand's workforce, this research aimed to assess AI literacy, AI anxiety, and AI acceptance among the workforces. In utilization of Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) framework as well as employing Structural

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Equation Modelling (SEM), the researcher was able to test the proposed hypotheses and examining the relationships between key factors such as performance expectancy, social influence, and trust of AI acceptance. In this study, using the data-driven approach helps in evaluation of the preparedness of the Thai workforce in adopting AI technologies in alignment with Thailand’s national AI strategy (2022-2027). The findings from this study can provide critical insights that altogether enhances AI integration into Thailand’s broader digital transformation efforts.

4.1 Measurement Model Assessment

As the measurement model was evaluated by using several key criteria in order to ensure reliability and validity of the constructs, this analysis focuses on internal consistency reliability, convergent validity and discriminant validity.

Internal Consistency Reliability

The assessment revealed strong internal consistency across every constructs. Composite Reliability (CR) values outpace the recommended threshold of 0.7, ranging from 0.791 to 0.868 which indicates a sturdy construct reliability. Similarly, Cronbach’s Alpha values also demonstrated high internal consistency to which consequently supports the reliability of the measurement scales.

Convergent Validity

The Average Variance Extracted or AVE values were also examined in order to appraise convergent validity. Every construct demonstrated AVE values above 0.5 threshold, as presented below:

- AI Literacy (AILI): 0.868
- AI Anxiety (AIAX): 0.830
- AI Acceptance (AIAC): 0.791

These values propose strong convergent validity which can be suggested that these items effectively measured their intended constructs and means.

Table 2

Reliability and Convergent Validity for multi-item constructs.

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>Items</i>	<i>Cronbach’s</i>	<i>rhoC</i>	<i>AVE</i>
<i>AI Literacy</i>	<i>11 items</i>	<i>0.985</i>	<i>0.986</i>	<i>0.868</i>
<i>AI Acceptance</i>	<i>2 items</i>	<i>0.736</i>	<i>0.883</i>	<i>0.791</i>
<i>AI Anxiety</i>	<i>9 items</i>	<i>0.974</i>	<i>0.978</i>	<i>0.830</i>
<i>INT</i>	<i>2 items</i>	<i>0.749</i>	<i>0.884</i>	<i>0.792</i>

rhoC = composite reliability; AVE = average variance extracted.

4.2 Structural Model

A PLS-SEM analysis was applied by using SmartPLS 3.0. Through the structural model analysis, there are several significant relationships have been revealed as per follows:

1. AI Literacy demonstrated the most potent effect on AI Anxiety ($\beta = -0.892$, $p < 0.001$), showing that there is a powerful negative relationship.
2. There is a positive influence on in between Performance Expectancy and AI Acceptance ($\beta = 0.370$, $p < 0.001$).

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3. AI Acceptance has a notable influence on Intention to Use ($\beta = 0.615, p < 0.001$).
4. The positive influence between AI Literacy and Performance Expectancy (PE) & Effort Expectancy (EE) ($\beta = 0.262, p < 0.001$), ($\beta = 0.327, p < 0.001$) respectively.

4.3 Mediating Effects

A mediating relationship has been revealed between these values:

1. AI Anxiety mediates the relationship between AI Literacy and AI Acceptance ($\beta = -0.250, p = 0.049$).

4.4 Hypothesis Testing Results

Through thorough analysis, eight out of twelve hypotheses have been supported:

1. H1.1 PE influences AI Acceptance
2. H1.2 EE influences AI Acceptance
3. H1.4 FC influences AI Acceptance
4. H1.5 PE influences PU
5. H1.7 AI Acceptance influences Intention to Use AI
6. H4 AI Literacy influences AI Anxiety
7. H5 AI Anxiety influences AI Acceptance
8. H6.1 AI Literacy influences Performance Expectancy (PE)
9. H6.2 AI Literacy influences Effort Expectancy (EE)
10. H7 AI Anxiety impact the relation between AI Literacy and AI Acceptance (Mediator)

The following four hypothesis, therefore, were not supported:

1. H1.3 SI influences AI Acceptance
2. H1.6 PE influences Intention to Use AI
3. H2 PS influences AI Acceptance

Table 3
Correlation result

<i>Constructs</i>	<i>AI Literacy</i>	<i>AI Anxiety</i>	<i>AI Acceptance</i>	<i>PE</i>	<i>EE</i>	<i>INT</i>
<i>AI Literacy</i>	1.000
<i>AI Anxiety</i>	-0.892	1.000
<i>AI Acceptance</i>	0.271	-0.276	1.000	.	.	.
<i>PE</i>	0.262	-0.261	0.122	1.000	.	.
<i>EE</i>	0.327	-0.255	0.474	0.293	1.000	.
<i>INT</i>	0.226	-0.274	0.61	0.177	0.294	1.000

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Figure 2
Result of test of structural model

Table 4
Structural model results

Hypothesis	Path	Path estimation (β)	t-stats
H1.1	PE influences AI Acceptance	0.122*	2.097
H1.2	EE influences AI Acceptance	0.370**	5.556
H1.3	SI influences AI Acceptance	0.061	0.97
H1.4	FC influences AI Acceptance	0.123*	1.957
H1.5	EE influences PE	0.293**	4.332
H1.6	PE influences Intention to Use AI	-0.017	0.33
H1.7	AI Acceptance influences Intention to Use AI	0.615**	16.101
H2	PS influences AI Acceptance	-0.002	0.037
H3	AI Literacy influences AI Acceptance	-0.194	1.492
H4	AI Literacy influences AI Anxiety	-0.892**	49.773
H5	AI Anxiety influences AI Acceptance	-0.250*	2.059
H6.1	AI Literacy influences Performance Expectancy (PE)	0.262**	5.515
H6.2	AI Literacy influences Effort Expectancy (EE)	0.327**	7.012

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$.

Table 5
Mediation results

Hypothesis	Path	Direct effect	Indirect effect	Mediation
H7	AI Anxiety impacts the relation between AI Literacy and AI Acceptance (mediator)	-0.250** ($t = 1.976$)	2.057** ($t = 2.057$)	Competitive Partial Mediation

* $p < .05$; ** $p < .01$.

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5. Discussion

In integrating the UTAUT framework with the AI-specific construct that provides constraining insights as to how AI can be integrated and accepted into Thailand's workforce. The findings provide an intricate relationship between the traditional UTAUT variable along with the new AI-specific factors. Altogether, they offer both theoretical and practical implications for digital transformations.

As Effort Expectancy can be derived as a crucial determinant of AI Acceptance ($\beta = 0.370$, $p < 0.001$) to which demonstrates that many Thai workers are willing to adopt AI technologies because of their perception of how ease or effortless it would be to utilize AI systems. It indicates that simplicity perception and user-friendliness of AI technologies play a significant role in their acceptance mindset among Thai workforces. This also aligns with UTAUT's fundamental basis while also extending its application to the AI context. Furthermore, the compelling relationships between effort expectancy and performance expectancy ($\beta = 0.293$, $p < 0.001$) further bolsters the significance of effort expectancy benefits in such technological acceptance even it not part of the original UTAUT model, but this finding underscores the importance of user-friendly design to promote AI acceptance and usefulness perception in workplace.

Another notable finding concerns the strong negative correlation between AI Literacy and AI Anxiety ($\beta = -0.892$, $p < 0.001$). This suggests that an enhanced AI knowledge can significantly reduce technology-related anxiety. The relationship between AI Literacy and AI Anxiety extends beyond the traditional UTAUT constructs to which that it provides the valuable insights into the psychological mechanism hidden in AI Acceptance. In the subsequent impact of AI Anxiety on AI Acceptance ($\beta = -0.250$, $p = 0.049$), the importance of addressing psychological barriers in technology adoption has been highlighted. Thus, fostering AI literacy could be a key strategy in mitigating anxiety, ultimately enhancing user acceptance and smoother integration of AI technologies.

In this research findings, the critical role of Facilitating Conditions or FC in AI acceptance ($\beta = 0.123$, $p = 0.048$) has been accentuated. This means that, fundamentally, organizational support is crucial to a successful AI implementation. This result further suggested that organizations should develop a comprehensive support program that allows employees to be supported in multiple fields from technical infrastructure, general training, and user support mechanism in order to facilitate smoother AI adoption. Apart from those findings, the research has also discovered that Social Influence or SI has shown a positive relationship ($\beta = 0.061$) but did not reach statistical significance ($p = 0.323$) which demonstrate that peer influence will enact a less crucial role in AI acceptance in comparison to other factors. This finding, in particular, diverges away from UTAUT applications which further suggest that AI adoption in Thai workforce may be more individually driven rather than socially driven.

This study also unveiled the empirical evidence or the significant relationship of AI Literacy on both Performance Expectancy (PE) and Effort Expectancy (EE) in Thailand's workforce which extends the UTAUT framework. The result exposed the positive influence of

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AI literacy in both Effort Expectancy (EE) ($\beta = 0.327$, $p < 0.001$, T-value = 7.100) and Performance Expectancy (PE) ($\beta = 0.262$, $p < 0.001$, T-value = 5.556) respectively which indicates that the higher AI literacy level could lead to improve ease of use perception and potential performance benefits from AI technology. These findings suggest that organization should prioritize AI literacy training initiative to enhance ease of use perception and usefulness perception for their workforces which will be practical approach for their change management strategies and educational initiatives in AI implementation and adoption.

Meanwhile, AI anxiety's mediating relationship with AI literacy and AI acceptance represents a new contribution to the technology's acceptance and literacy. The mediating effects further indicate that organizations should then focuses on both enhancing AI literacy and addressing anxiety concerns in order to encourage successful AI implementation and integration in organization.

While these findings attempt to provide a deeper understanding of Thailand's workforce adoption of AI technologies, it is important to keep in mind that it shall be interpreted within Thailand's unique cultural and technological context. The strong influence of Effort Expectancy and Facilitating Conditions is well aligned with Thailand's practical approach of AI technologies adoption where benefits and institutional support plays a deeper, critical roles in the acceptance of such technologies.

While this research has paved paths for future research, many non-significant relationships that this research has unveiled will warrant further research and examination in the future. For instance, the relationship between Social Influence and Perceived Security where further examination in relation to different cultural contexts or industry sectors shall be implemented. Moreover, longitudinal studies could further provide insights into how AI acceptance will evolve over time to adapt to AI technologies becoming more integrated into workplace environments.

Thru this research's vigorous methodological approach, the combination between UTAUT and AI-specific constructs has provided a validated framework for future research in relation to technology acceptances. The reliability and validity measures substantiate the model's practicality and applicability in further studies about AI acceptance in emerging economies.

However, as the research has provided valuable insights, there are certain limitations that shall be acknowledged. First, the cross-sectional nature of data collection may not completely capture the dynamic nature of AI acceptance over time. Moreover, since this research is focusing on Thailand's workforce, there may be limitations apply in generalizing the findings to other cultural contexts or other technological environments.

These findings have also suggested that policymakers should indeed focus on developing a more comprehensive AI literacy programs as well as addressing AI anxiety-related factors. The strong correlation between AI literacy and Effort Expectancy or EE ($\beta = 0.327$, $p < 0.001$) further implies that educational initiatives should be underlined wit practical implications and performance benefits.

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Overall, this research has contributed prominently in both theoretical understanding and practical implementation of AI technologies in the workplace environment. In the context of emerging economies like Thailand where findings like these will provide a foundation of AI acceptance enhancement and ultimately a successful implementation in organizational settings.

6. Conclusion

This research marks significant theoretical and practical contributions to the understanding of AI acceptance in Thailand's workforce through thorough assessment of AI literacy, anxiety, and acceptance by examining the factors that influences the adoption of AI technologies using the Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAUT) framework. Furthermore, the finding provides crucial insights into the dynamic in AI adoption, in relations to Thailand's national AI strategy (2022-2027), which aims to foster an AI-ready workforce.

The results shows that AI acceptance is further driven by a more complex factors with Effort Expectancy and AI literacy playing a significant role in acceptance of AI technologies. Many relationships, such as AI literacy and AI anxiety which possess a negative correlation, can be used to exemplify that educational initiatives should be focused and enhanced on both technical knowledge and psychological barrier as it is can now be implied that workers with possession of higher levels of AI literacy demonstrated greater confidence in AI tools, in alignment with the hypothesis that performance expectancy and effort expectancy can positively influence AI acceptance and reduce negative influence that could generate AI anxiety. In addition, AI literacy leads positive result in term of ease of use and usefulness perception. Once workforces acquire adequate AI related skill and knowledge, they are aware of potential advantages and benefits which could apply for their lives and tends to interact more with AI technology. Furthermore, the study confirmed that AI anxiety can act as a mediating factor between AI literacy and AI acceptance. Through educational initiative and increasing familiarity with AI tools, however, organizations can enhance AI acceptance and reduce AI-related anxiety. The findings also finds that the importance of social influence and facilitating conditions can play a crucial role in AI acceptance, of organizational environments where supports from peers and leaders holds firm ground.

As much as the research has uncovered, however, the study has some limitations. In particular, of its cross-sectional nature and the focused implication on Thai workforce's context. While future research may benefit from this research's longitudinal studies examining how AI acceptance evolves over time, it may also expand into new territories of comparative studies across different cultural contexts. Additionally, some factors such as Social Influence and Perceived Security highlights the needs for further investigation into different settings as well.

From the policy perspective, these findings further propose the need for coordinative efforts in enhancement of AI literacy and reduction of AI-related anxieties that could hinders AI-adoption and integration on the national level. This strong relationship between AI literacy and various given constructs and factors has provided that implementing educational initiatives should be a priority in Thailand workforce's AI integration strategy.

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Overall, this research has contributed to both the academic understanding as well as practical implementation of how AI technologies could be integrated into the workplace. From the validated framework that provides the foundational understanding for future studies to offering actionable insights for organization and policymakers alike to navigate this digital transformation, this research's findings underscore the importance of finding a holistic approach that addresses both technical and human aspects of AI implementation. Ultimately, as AI technologies continues to reshape and the workplace environment, this research will serve as a valuable guideline in developing an effective strategy to enhance AI acceptance and implementation success in emerging economies like Thailand.

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